

ISic0795

I.Sicily inscription 0795

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8728

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κ(οῖντε) · Κορνιφίκι
2. Στεφανῆφορε
3. χρηστὲ · καὶ · ἄμενπτε
4. χαῖρε
5. [Ἔ]ζησε · ἔτη · ιβ · μῆ(νας) · θ ·

Apparatus

Text of Ferrua 1941

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493914

EDCS 41300090

PHI 175706

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1975.0455

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 108

Ferrua, A 1941. Analecta sicula. *Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 268 no.40

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0795. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339122>